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Empowering the future: Incentivizing technical teaching in Ebonyi state's post-primary schools

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Abstract

This study was to determine motivational initiatives required for improving the supply of technical teachers in post-primary schools of Ebonyi state. Three research questions were developed in line with what the study sought to find out. Questionnaire was also developed, validated by experts and used to gather data from 149 respondents. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions; and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that establishment of free technical teachers training programme and technical education board; proper funding of vocational teacher's programme and introduction of technical teacher's salary scheme are initiative from government for improving the supply of technical teachers. Communities could improve the supply of technical teachers through provision of safe supportive training environment and facilities; and creation of awareness for vocational teachers' education programme. Companies' initiative identified are provision of co-operative and continuing education and partnership with vocational teacher institution for provision of teaching facilities. It was then recommended that government should establish free technical teachers' training programme in the state. Also, community and companies should collaborate with vocational teacher institutions for the supply of facilities and awareness campaign on the importance and need for technical teachers.

Keywords: Motivational Initiatives; Technical Teachers; Vocational Education; Technical Teachers' Training; Post-Primary Schools

1. Introduction

Technical teachers in post primary schools of Ebonyi State play vital roles in implementing the 6-3-3-4 system of Education. They require incentives which enhance readiness to embark or venture into technical teaching jobs. Some of readiness are in form of abilities that initiate and empower individuals to choose, train and start the teaching job. Initiatives are therefore ideas and activities generated and utilized to ginger up people to start doing something (Hornby [1]). In the context of this study, initiatives are activities used by government, communities or companies to solve the problem of inadequate technical teachers. Baike [2] said that initiatives that increase the supply of technical teachers are mostly in form of motivation or incentives.

Motivation stimulates people to action to achieve a desired task. Thus, Adedeji, [3], explained motivation as a process that arouses, energies, directs and sustain behaviour and performance. Initiatives that encourage technical teachers to stay on the job thereby attracting more people into the job, could be regarded as motivational initiatives. Motivational initiatives are therefore those actions put in place either by governments or their agencies, proprietors, companies and communities to improve the supply of technical teachers and help present teachers stay on job. Akinwumi [4] stated that initiatives from government that could motivate people into vocational teaching job include establishment of free

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Technical Teachers Training programmes (TTTP), vocational Teachers Information Centres, (VTIC), and Technology Education Research Centres (TERC). Bennell [5] added that proper funding of vocational teacher education programmes, payment of vocational-technical teachers' special allowance, and giving technical teachers opportunities to participate in professional technology association could stimulate people into teaching vocational subjects.

In his view, Francis [6] said that communities initiatives towards motivating people into technical teachers' training are vital. Some of the motivational initiatives from communities according to Francis [6] are provision of supportive atmosphere for technical teachers training, safe training environment and procurement of materials for training. In the other hand, companies could provide some initiatives that when properly utilized will enhance supply of technical teachers. Some of the company's initiative are provision of cooperative education for vocational teachers practical training, provision of continuing education in form of workshop and conferences on new technologies for technical teachers, and provision of initiatives programmes such as technology education information centres and consultancy services, (Omar [7]). The author remarked that absence of motivational initiatives could militate against the supply of technical teachers. In the context of this study supply could mean the use of initiatives and incentives to buff up the number of technical teachers on (the jobs in post primary schools of Ebonyi State. In Ebonyi State, technical teachers function mostly in post primary schools such as science schools, technical colleges, model secondary schools, comprehensive secondary schools and vocational schools. These schools provide enough teaching jobs for technical teachers. Olaitain, Nwachukwu, Igbo, Onyemachi and Ekong [8] explained job as a position or total array of responsibilities which every individual engages to earn a living. The job of technical teacher in Ebonyi State post primary schools include teaching, conducting practical/experiments, testing, evaluating, instilling discipline, counselling and directing students. To make the job lighter, the supply of teachers need to be increased.

In the opinion of Hornby [1], to improve something means making it more in amount, number or efficiency. Thus, in the context of this study improving the supply of technical teachers means to make serving technical teachers more in number or adequate) to teach prevocational, vocational and technical subjects in post primary schools of Ebonyi State. There is a great need to expand the number of vocational-technical teachers in the state because at present enrolments in schools are expanding and laboratories/workshops are in size and equipment (Egbe [9]). Eze [10] said that increase in supply of vocational teachers in Ebonyi State could be through regular recruitment of teachers and helping teachers to stay on technical teaching jobs.

This study identified some motivational initiatives that could be employed to improve the supply of technical teachers. If these initiatives are properly utilized, there is every likelihood that many students may want to enroll in technical teachers' education programmes with a view to becoming teachers, thereby reducing the level of scarcity of vocational teachers in the state.

In pursuance of the objectives of the National Policy on Education (Federal Republication of Nigeria [11]) about vocational/technical education, Ebonyi State government established vocational/technical schools to train students in skills in various areas of technology. However, it has been observed by the researcher that many post primary schools in the state do not have enough teachers to teach pre-vocational, vocational and technical subjects. As a result, teachers get involved in shift before they could organize practical to their ever-teaming students offering vocational subjects. There appear to be a feeling of over work by the teachers.

Again, Eze [10] remarked that the present technical teachers on the job have negative feeling about their jobs due to some suspected reasons such as irregular payment of salary, delayed promotion and over work caused by class shifts. He stated further that these teachers are looking for better job opportunities for their comfort thereby giving off teaching in schools.

If this situation is allowed to happen there is possibility of increase unemployment, delinquency and crime among secondary schools graduates and their peers in Ebonyi State. To arrest this situation it is necessary to find better means of increasing the supply of technical teachers and retaining present vocational teachers on the job, hence the study.

The purpose of this study is to identify motivational initiatives that could be used to increase the supply of vocational teachers in post primary schools of Ebonyi State for effective teaching of vocational/technical subjects.

Specifically, the study sought to

- Identify initiatives and incentive from the government that could be used to expand the supply of technical teachers
- Identify initiatives that communities could provide to enhance the supply of technical teachers.

- Identify rewarding contributions from companies that could help to improve the supply of vocational teachers.
- The Hypothesis of the study is:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of technical teachers, officers of ministry of education and company executive on initiatives and incentives required from government that could expand the supply of technical teachers.

2. Material and Method

The study was carried out in Ebonyi state. The state was chosen for this study due to great demand for vocational teachers in the area.

The population for the study was 341 persons. This consisted of, 96 technical teachers. 39 senior officers of ministry of education, 170 community leaders, and 36 company executives. The entire 39 officers of ministry of education and the 36-company executive were utilized for the study, while purposive sampling was used to select 40 technical teachers and 34 community leaders; giving a sample of 149 respondents.

Questionnaire was developed and validated by experts. It was used to collect data from 149 respondents. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized for testing the hypothesis.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 Mean Ratings of Responses on the Initiatives and Incentives from Government to Expand the Supply of Vocational Teachers

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Establishment of free technical teachers training programme for both serving and intending teachers in the state (TTTP) will expand supply of teachers.	3.21	0.57	Accepted
2.	Instant recruitment of vocational teachers on graduation will improve the supply of teachers.	2.97	0.63	Accepted
3.	Introduction of technical teacher's salary scale will stimulate more into technical teaching and thus enhance the supply of teachers	2.71	0.67	Accepted
4.	Good funding of vocational teachers' programmes will attract people into vocational teaching job.	2.88	0.65	Accepted
5.	Giving vocational teachers opportunities to participate in professional technology education association will attract more people into the job.	2.51	0.73	Accepted
6.	Assurance of job security will make people choose, train/ and stay on vocational teaching job.	3.11	0.60	Accepted
7.	Provision of fringe benefits like car and housing loans, free medical services and gratuity will stimulate people into vocational teaching job.	3.13	0.61	Accepted
8.	Improvement in teachers' status by appointing teachers as permanent secretaries, education secretaries and others will attract people into the job	2.58	0.72	Accepted
9.	Government establishment of vocational technical education board will help to improve supply of vocational	2.99	0.69	accepted

From the data in table 1 above, all the 9 items have their means above 2.50 which is the cut off point. This signifies that each of the nine items is accepted as government motivational initiatives for improving the supply of technical teachers at post primary school level. The standard deviations of the items range from 0.57 to 0.72, showing that the respondents are close to one another in their responses.

These findings agree with the views of Akinwumi [4] that initiatives from government that could motivate people into technical teaching job are establishment of free technical teachers' training programmes, vocational teachers' training

programmes, vocational teachers' information centres, and technology education research centres. The findings also agree with the opinions of Bennell [5] that proper funding of technical education and payment of special allowance to technical teachers will stimulate people into choosing vocational teaching job.

Table 2 Mean Ratings of the Respondents' Opinions on Community's Initiatives for Enhancing the Supply off Technical Teachers

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Communities' collaboration with schools for provision of safe supportive environment for technical teachers will improve their supply,	2.79	0.68	Accepted
2.	Communities' initiative in mobilization of technical teachers' training resources like land labour; fund and facilities will improve supply of teachers	2.91	0.63	Accepted
3.	Communities' initiative in establishing vocational teacher institutions will enhance the supply of technical teachers	2.91	0.63	Accepted
4.	communities' provision of essential start-up information to intending technical teachers will help, to create awareness and then enhance supply	3.11	0.58	Accepted
5.	Community's initiative in establishing technical colleges will stimulate people to join technical teacher's training to increase the number of teachers	2.65	0.71	Accepted
6.	Establishment of community skill acquisition centres will help to improve the supply of technical teachers	2.43	0.99	Not accepted

Data in table 2 above show that five items have means above 2.50 which is cut-off point. This indicates that community's initiative in provision safe training enrolment, training resources and essential information about technical education will enhance the supply of teachers. Again, community's efforts in establishing vocational teachers' institutions and technical colleges will stimulate people into vocational teachers' education. These findings agree with the views of Francis [6] that provision of safe supportive atmosphere and training materials by the community could increase the number of technical teachers. But, the respondents did not agree that establishment of community skill acquisition centres will improve the supply of technical teachers.

Table 3 Mean Ratings of the Respondents' Opinions on the Initiatives from Companies that could Improve the Supply of Technical Teachers

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Companies' partnership with vocational teachers' institutions for designing, providing and servicing teaching tools, equipment and machines will improve supply of teachers.	2.77	0.59	Accepted
2.	Companies' provision of cooperative education for vocational students teachers' practical training will enhance their supply.	3.01	0.55	Accepted
3.	Companies' provision of continuing education in form of seminars and workshops on new technologies for technical teachers will help to retain them on the job. '	2.82	0.58	Accepted
4.	Companies partnership, with vocational teachers institutions for developing advance curricula that meet market requirements will improve supply of teachers	2.69		Accepted
5.	Companies' provision of capitation allowances or stipend to technical teachers on training will improve then supply.	2.76	0.60	Accepted
6.	Companies provision of financial assistance to vocational teachers education programmes will improve the supply of teachers	3.33	0.54	Accepted
7.	Industrial fellowship in form of joint research projects or thesis will improve the supply of technical teachers.	2.51	0.79	Accepted
8.	Companies provision of small business training to nascent entrepreneurs will improve supply of technical teachers	2.44	0.83	Accepted

Data in table 2 above show that five items have means above 2.50 which is cut-off point. This indicates that community's initiative in provision safe training enrolment, training resources and essential information about technical education will enhance the supply of teachers. Again, community's efforts in establishing vocational teachers' institutions and technical colleges will stimulate people into vocational teachers' education. These findings agree with the views of Francis [6] that provision of safe supportive atmosphere and training materials by the community could increase the number of technical teachers. But the respondents did not agree that establishment of community skill acquisition centres will improve the supply of technical teachers.

From table 3 above, seven items have means above 2.50, showing that each of the seven items is accepted as a rewarding contribution from company for improving the supply of teachers. The findings on companies' contributions towards improving supply of technical teachers in form of provision of financial support, training resources and continuing education programmes are in keeping with the views of Ojah [12] that companies' provision of financial support to vocational teachers' institutions will improve the supply of technical teachers. But, one item has a mean of 2.44, indicating that it is not accepted as a motivational initiative from company for improving supply of teachers.

The close range of standard deviation from 0.54 to 0.83, indicates that the respondents are close in their 'opinions and not far from the means.

Table 4 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the mean score responses of the respondents on motivational initiatives from Government that could expand die supply of technical teachers

Source of variance	Df	Sum of squares	Mean Squares	f-call	f-critical	significance	Decision
Between	3	0.00596.	0.001987				
Within groups	145	154.182	1.13229	0.00175	2.60	NS	Accepted
Total	148	164.18796					

From table, 4, the critical value off with 3 and 145 degrees of freedom at 0.05, level of significance is 2.60. Since the calculated f-value of 0.00175 is smaller than the critical value (2.60) the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant difference in the opinions of the respondents on motivational initiatives from government for improving the supply of technical teachers

4. Conclusion

This study investigated motivational initiatives required to improve the supply teachers in Ebonyi teachers are in short supply and it is hard to retain them on the job. The study identified means of improving the supply and retains vocational teachers on the job in form of initiatives and incentives from government, communities and companies such as establishment of more vocational teacher institution, free technical teachers training programme and proper funding of the programme. Also payment of special allowance for vocational teachers and retaining promotion and payment of salary are incentives identified for retaining them on them on the job. Recommendations are; therefore made that government should establish free technical teachers training programme (TTTP) for both serving and intending teachers and; adequately fund the programme Again, government in collaboration with community should organize awareness campaign on the importance of vocational-education and need for more teachers in this field.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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